

EFFECTIVENESS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION TOOLS IN PREVENTING OCCUPATIONAL DISEASES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7903942>

Abstract. This article is intended to provide methodological assistance in the activities of enterprises, organizations and institutions to increase labor productivity and extend the labor activity of the population.

Key words: occupational diseases, osteochondrosis, hypodynamia, complex of gymnastic exercises.

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ СРЕДСТВ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ВОСПИТАНИЯ В ПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ

Аннотация. Данная статья призвана оказать методическую помощь в деятельности предприятий, организаций и учреждений по повышению производительности труда и расширению трудовой активности населения.

Ключевые слова: профессиональные заболевания, остеохондроз, гиподинамия, комплекс гимнастических упражнений.

Introduction. For one person's actions and spent health reserves recovery, healthy generation save to stay and life extension, vital activity provide and own to health from childhood to old age until the period reasonable in relation to be orientation need _

But It is known that the present period very a lot people due to hypodynamia (inactivity). surface coming from diseases suffering smokes _

Basically, to these a lot movement demand which does not field representatives includes (teachers, medicine employees, engineers, sellers, cargo carriers, office employees on the conveyor workers, operators, drivers, on the computer workers and etc.).

Long term motionless in case while standing or while sitting, less moving in the organism substances exchange, blood rotation subsides. Foot muscles become weak and tall to change take will come and less moving occupation owners from more headaches complaint they do

Current in the day mental and physical downloads reasonable distribution, healthy marriage style conduct and physical exercises with regularly respectively engage in each one of a person successful life of activity indispensable is a fragment.

But, mostly, people health seriously derailed _ only when healthy marriage style and physical exercises to perform they start, although regularly respectively simple physical exercises perform to our health own positive effect shows.

Physical education and with public sports regularly engage in and healthy marriage style according to vital skills formation through each one in the citizen to the disease against strong immune system appear to be provide, harmful giving up habits, right eating principles action make, restore and rehabilitation works and public physical activity events systematic and efficient organize to do directed wide handy affairs done is increasing.

Uzbekistan Republic President of October 30 , 2020 " Healthy marriage style wide app reach and public sports more development measures on" No. PF -6099 In his decree each one family , neighborhood and in the district (city), before school , general medium , medium special , professional and higher education in institutions and another in organizations physical education and with public sports to engage in conditions create , population different of groups healthy to eat has been needs to satisfy which provides conditions create , contains salt, sugar and fat quantity a lot has been and doughy food and sweets , bread products consumption to do shortening , harmful from habits , in particular alcohol and tobacco products consumption refrain from doing the way with to the disease playing , too much weight conditions (obesity) and premature death to reach reduce in order to row affairs take is going [1, 2].

Research purpose : healthy marriage style promote in doing physical education tools through work activity efficiency increase _

Research tasks :

- in the population occupation diseases to determine and generalization ;
- work in the activity to be given physical exercises and downloads volume of the population physical to health effect to determine
- occupation diseases prevention in getting , special physical of exercises population to the organism effect degrees to determine
- **Research results and his discussion .**

Someone is someone occupation with regularly engaged in since , his in the organism that's it to the profession special has been some diseases developed goes _ This Diseases are usually the same of the profession to himself special features , regular work in the process of the organism certain to the member descender weights , different harmful substances and another reasons as a result appear will be

Statistics _ According to the work standing in the process without work who runs occupation in the owners of veins varicose veins expansion is being observed . Last at times such to illness playing young people between too wide spread to him subject to of those who 3540 years old on average organize is doing

Job in the process sitting down work who runs occupation in the owners as a result of inactivity (hypodynamia). the body of weight increase too is being observed . Job in the process sitting down work 3700 occupations _ owners between conducted request to the results according to 55 percent of them the body of weight from the increase complaint did including 40 percent _ _ to this exactly professional activity during face what came emphasized . Known office _ _ employees (69 percent) , engineers (56 percent) , teachers (51 percent) and lawyers (48 percent) are permanent respectively mother so to the problem face they come on the surface special work of developed gymnastic exercises different ratios _ efficiency to determine in order to everyone experience groups for content same special _ physical exercises set work released , however special and general developer exercises different in options applied . Job in the process sitting down work who runs occupation of the owners the body of weight increased level looking to groups separated . of employees obesity to levels depending on I , II, III and IV levels employees choose received _

TVI (body weight index on average 18.5-24.9 kg/m²)

TVI from 25 to 30 kg/m² - 1st degree obesity ;

- TVI from 30 to 35 kg/m² - 2nd degree obesity ;
- TVI from 35 to 40 kg/m² - 3rd degree obesity ;
- TVI above 40 - 4 degree obesity , severe obesity ;

In the experiment the first in turn , of the employee the body weight determining the index (TVI). necessary _ TVI through the following formula is : $\text{weight (kg) height to the square increased divided by length (l)}$. For example , the participant weight 84 kg and height is 1.65 m, then $\text{TVI} = 84:(1.65 \times 1.65) = 30.9$. It is level I obesity will be

I level obesity 12 available _

II level obesity there are 13 people

III level obesity there are 14 people

IV level obesity 15 available _ a total of 54 employees experience to the group sorted received _ n=54 Study during work developed special exercises from the complex use to the road in putting certain table work released _ (To the table mainly 4 groups in employees special exercises set according to training 3 times a week take went and their duration from 5 to 10 minutes organize did .) Obesity to levels looking local to the muscles effect doer special exercises choose received _ Employees age , gender , functional status , obesity degrees for special exercises standards work released _ Received results known one of muscles in places to the muscles efficient effect that it will shows .

In research work in the process sitting down work who runs occupation owners for work release gymnastics exemplary exercises from the complex was used . in a chair sitting and to him hand with relied on without , legs at the tip standing , hands to the side , then to the top let's raise , deep breath we can previous to the situation back breath released (2-4 repetitions 3 times a week with will be done . Repetitions rest for 3-4 seconds in between);

1- initial condition hands above zamok in case legs at the tip quarrel exercises (3-4 repetitions 3 times a week with will be done . Repetitions rest for 3-4 seconds in between);

2- initial condition in a chair sitting in case feet on the ground. 1st left foot forward 2-second stretched , 2-d.x. 3- right leg forward 2-second extended , 4-d.x. (3-4 repetitions 3 times a week 4th second is done with . Repetitions 2-4 seconds rest in between);

3- in a chair sitting in case left hand from above right hand from the pass behind combined without 10 seconds stretched out stand up (3-4 repetitions 3 times a week with hands from the count after 10 seconds will be executed instead . Repetitions rest for 3-4 seconds in between);

5-initial state left hand above right hand at the waist 1- turn to the right , 2-d.x. 3- hands situation replace to the left bending , 4-d.x. (2-4 repetitions 3 times a week with will be done . Repetitions rest for 3-4 seconds in between);

Physical exercises from being used after physical preparation indicator analysis that's it showed that those involved obesity degrees according to from pedagogical experience in groups after results improved , that is positive change observed . This research during conducted special from exercises use 42.8 % of employees are healthy the body your weight to the norm what came showed and their physical education and with sports engage in possible showed .

Conclusion. Below shown employees gymnastics exercises regularly respectively perform as a result of osteochondrosis (salt accumulation in the joints), spine in the part hernia , hypertension, diabetes , cancer , osteoporosis , cancer , obesity , body internal of members wrong performance (art of exchange deterioration) as diseases development risk reducing work _

productivity increases . Final to the conclusion coming If so , research with 54 employees at the beginning training we started and 30 people in 6 months employee at 2 levels left _ 24 employees of II, III, IV level from obesity to I degree was conducted . This common an increase of 44.4% in the account observed .

REFERENCES

1. Шерали Хошимович Гофуров, Баходир Хошимович Гофуров ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА 5X5 ФУТБОЛ СПОРТ ТУРИНИ ОММАЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ КЎРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИДА НУҚСОНИ БОР ШАХСЛАР ҲАРАКАТ ФАОЛЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zbekistonda-5x5-futbol-sport-turini-ommalashtirish-or-ali-k-rish-obiliyatida-nu-soni-bor-shahslar-arakat-faolligini-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022)
2. Sherali Xoshimovich G'Ofurov, Bahodir Xoshimovich G'Ofurov NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA POG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nogironlar-aravachasidan-foydalanadigan-umurtqa-pog-onasi-shikastlangan-yoshlarning-adaptiv-jismoniy-tarbiyasi> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022).
3. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov MALAKALI SPRINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/malakali-sprinterchilarning-sport-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 13.12.2022).
4. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 13.12.2022).
5. Sherali Hoshimovich G. Ofurov Qisqa masofaga yuguruvchi sportchilarni mashg'ulotlarini rivojlantirishning usullari //Scientific progress. – 2021. – №. 8.
6. ЖИСМОНИЙ Л., НАЗАРИЙ Т., РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ С. Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. № Special Issue 1 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bolalar-tserebral-falazhida-zhismoniy-tayyorgarlikni-mash-ulot-zharayonida-va-ilmiy-nazariy-so-ada-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 12.01. 2022).
7. BOLALAR V. A. O'smirlar SPOR МАКТАБЛАРИДА SPORCHILAR TAYYORLANISHINI TAKILISH BOSHLANGAN MASHG'ULOT GURUHI GofurovSh //X. Fan-Sportga. – 2020. – №. 5. – С. 38-40.
8. Гофуров Ш. NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA POG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI //МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКАЯ ОНЛАЙН КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ. – 2021. – Т. 4. – С. 24.

9. ЕОФУРОВ Ш. МАКТАБЛАРИДА БОШЛАНЧИ ТАЙЁРЛОВ ГУРУ^ ИДА ШУҒУЛЛАНУВЧИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАР МАШҒУЛОТЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ. – 2020.
10. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O. MALAKALI SPRINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – №. 4.
11. Gofurov S. X. et al. A STRATIFIED APPROACH IN IMPROVING THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF GIRLS WITH DISABILITIES //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 12. – С. 179-189.
12. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O. et al. Scientific progress. 2022. № 1 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 04.02. 2022).
13. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL АТЛЕТИКА MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
14. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL АТЛЕТИКА MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
15. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O., Dilshod Baxtiyor O. G., Li Baxtiyorov U. A. S. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni yengil atletika mashqlari orqali mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etish //Scientific progress. – 2022. – №. 1.
16. Dilshod Baxtiyorovich Baxtiyorov AMPUNTANT FUTBOLCHILARNI JISMONIY TARBIYA VOSITALARI VA USLUBIYATI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ampuntant-futbolchilarni-jismoniy-tarbiya-vositalari-va-uslubiyati> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
17. Hoshimovich G. S., Duszhanov B. M., Abdumavlanovich T. U. IMPROVEMENT OF THE TRAINING PROCESS OF FLIGHT AND ATHLETS IN THE INITIAL TRAINING GROUP OF YOUTH //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 12. – С. 163-176.
18. ҒОФУРОВ Ш. Х. БОЛАЛАР ВА ЎСМИРЛАР СПОРТ МАКТАБЛАРИДА БОШЛАНЧИ ТАЙЁРЛОВ ГУРУҲИДА ШУҒУЛЛАНУВЧИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАР МАШҒУЛОТЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ //Фан-Спортга. – 2020. – №. 5. – С. 38-40.
19. Sherali Xoshimovich G'Ofurov, Baxodir Xoshimovich G'Ofurov NOGIRONLAR АRAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURТQA POG'ONASI

- SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nogironlar-aravachasidan-foydalanadigan-umurtqa-pog-onasi-shikastlangan-yoshlarning-adaptiv-jismoniy-tarbiyasi> (дата обращения: 09.01.2023).
20. Gofurov, S. X., Berdiyeva, C. A., Berdiyev, S. D., & Atabayev, A. N. (2022). A STRATIFIED APPROACH IN IMPROVING THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF GIRLS WITH DISABILITIES. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(12), 179-189.
21. Hoshimovich, G. S., Hoshimovich, G. B., & Ibragim o'g'li, K. S. (2022). Differentiated Approach to Improving the Physical Qualities of Students With Disabilities. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 15, 213-223.
22. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov QISQA MASOFAGA YUGURUVCHI SPORTCHILARNI MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/qisqa-masofaga-yuguruvchi-sportchilarni-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 09.01.2023).
23. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022)
24. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov MALAKALI SPRINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/malakali-sprinterchilarning-sport-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).
25. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov QISQA MASOFAGA YUGURUVCHI SPORTCHILARNI MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/qisqa-masofaga-yuguruvchi-sportchilarni-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).
26. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).
27. Gofurov S. X. et al. A STRATIFIED APPROACH IN IMPROVING THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF GIRLS WITH DISABILITIES //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 179-189.

28. Hoshimovich G. S., Duszhanov B. M., Abdumavlanovich T. U. IMPROVEMENT OF THE TRAINING PROCESS OF FLIGHT AND ATHLETES IN THE INITIAL TRAINING GROUP OF YOUTH //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 163-176.
29. Hoshimovich G. S. et al. Differentiated Approach to Improving the Physical Qualities of Students With Disabilities //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – Т. 15. – С. 213-223.
30. Шерали Хошимович Гофуров, Баходир Хошимович Гофуров ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА 5X5 ФУТБОЛ СПОРТ ТУРИНИ ОММАЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ КЎРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИДА НУҚСОНИ БОР ШАХСЛАР ҲАРАКАТ ФАОЛЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zbekistonda-5x5-futbol-sport-turini-ommalashtirish-or-ali-k-rish-obiliyatida-nu-soni-bor-shahslar-arakat-faolligini-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).
31. Gofurov S. SPECIALIZES IN ORGANIZING ATHLETIC EXERCISE GROUPS APPLICATION OF EXERCISES //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 659-662.
32. Khoshimovich G. S. Rowing With the Help of Special Equipment and Methods of Balance Development in Canoeing //Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 26-30.
33. Gofurov S. H., Tashpolatova K. G., Ollaberganov S. E. University Students Methods of Preparation for Sport of Powerlifting //Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 31-35.
34. Teacher, Gafurov Sherali Khoshimovich. "ROWING WITH THE HELP OF SPECIAL EQUIPMENT AND METHODS OF BALANCE DEVELOPMENT IN CANOEING." *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management* 2.1 (2023).
35. Makhammadjonovich, Giyasov Temur, Gofurov Sherali Hoshimovich, and Palvanov Avazkhan Abdullaevich. "PHYSICAL FITNESS OF LONG JUMPER 14-15 YEAR OLD ATHLETES ENGAGED IN TRAINING GROUP INCREASING EFFICIENCY." *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management* 1.1 (2022).
36. Шерзод Абдурахмонович Абдиев, Рухиддин Фахриддинович Одилов, Шерали Хошимович Гофуров, Н. Ш. Бобомуродов ИМКОНИЯТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИ УЛОҚТИРУВЧИЛАРНИНГ МАШҒУЛОТ ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №10. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/imkoniyati-cheklangan-engil-atletikachi-ulo-tiruvchilarning-mash-ulot-yuklamalarini-rezhalashtirish> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).
37. Sherali Xoshimovich G'Ofurov, Sherzod Abdurahmonovich Abdiyev, Bahodir Xoshimovich G'Ofurov, Azizbek Xoshimjon O'G'Li Uzoqov ИМКОНИЯТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН БОЛАЛАР НАЙОТДА АДАПТИВИЙ ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАРБИЯНИНГ О'РНИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №10. URL:

- <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/imkoniyati-cheklangan-bolalar-hayotida-adaptiviy-jismoniy-tarbiyaning-o-rni> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).
38. Sherali Xoshimovich G'Ofurov, Ваходир Xoshimovich G'Ofurov NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA POG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nogironlar-aravachasidan-foydalanadigan-umurtqa-pog-onasi-shikastlangan-yoshlarning-adaptiv-jismoniy-tarbiyasi> (дата обращения: 04.05.2023).